

A Comparison between Sprinters and Long Distance Runner with in Circulatory Indices

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to compare the circulatory indices between sprinters and long distance runners. The subjects were selected from the Lakshmibai National Institute of Physical Education and training centers, who had participated last 3 years at All India Athletic Championship for this study. Twenty (20) sprinters and long distance runners were selected as the subject for the study. Selected circulatory indices such as resting pulse rate, blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic) and pulse pressure. To see the significant difference of selected circulatory indices variables among the sprinters and long distance runners the analysis of "mean, standard deviation and t test" was applied at 0.05 level of significance. As per the finding Long distance runners were better than Sprinters on resting pulse rate, blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic). No significant changes were found in pulse pressure of the Sprinters and Long distance runners. Hence, it can be concluded that the physical activity may help the athletes by involving the adaptation power of their cardio-vascular.

Keywords: Circulatory Indices, Sprinters, Long Distance Runners

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INTRODUCTION

By nature human beings are competitive and aspires from excellence in every field. Sport is not an exception, changes are the order of the day. Changes are taking place every day in every walk of life. Life of people, their philosophy, ways of living etc. are undergoing changes due to basic and applied research in various fields. New techniques are developed in laboratories and scientific methods are applied to obtain the level of performance. Sports by their very nature are enjoyable, challenging, absorbing and require a certain amount of skill and physical condition (Seaton *et al.*, 1956)

With all round advancement in the science of sports the new disciplines are emerging with micro-specialization. The elements, of scientific basis of selection are being inducted in the procedure of selection of athletes at various levels in some of the advanced countries. The knowledge from many scientific disciplines is being used for improving criteria for the selection of talents. The physical educationists have designed test procedures for evaluating the fitness of young children.

Among all the factors, the physiological characteristics play an important role for the attainment of high level sports performance. Among the various physiological parameters, cardiovascular efficiency forms the basis to undertake sports efforts successfully.

Cardio-vascular efficiency reflects the capacity of an individual to undertake and continues physical efforts of sub-maximal nature for a relatively longer period of time. To measure cardio-vascular efficiency, tests of physical works capacity and VO₂ max have been developed to use in laboratory and field situations to assists the scientist, physical educators and coaches (Daniel, 1985).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Participants

A group of forty (N = 40) male All India Athletic Inter university level in the Sprinting and long distance running event were in this study. The subjects were divided into two groups. i.e., sprinters and long distance runners. Each group comprised of 20 subjects. The average age of the students ranged from 21 to 24 years. For measuring the breath holding time, resting respiratory rate and pulse rate, the stop watches were used. The suppliers, Krishna Watch Company, Mumbai, assured the accurate calibration of there watches. Blood pressure of the subjects was measured using Stethoscope and Sphygmomanometer. The equipments were manufactured by a competent form, Biological concern, Kalkota. Thus the instrument reliability was assumed.

The subjects were clearly informed and well acquainted with the requirement of the study and the testing procedure. The testing on variables was conducted at the human performance Laboratory of Lakshmbai National Institute of Physical Education, NERC, Guwahati. The entire testing procedure took about 4 days.

The collected data were statistically analyzed using Medcalc software. Student's t-test was used to assess the between group differences. The level of $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS

The mean value of circulatory indices of sprinters and long distance runners is presented in Table 1.

It is seen from the table 1 that the mean values of resting pulse rate and pulse pressure were lower for sprinters and higher in Long distance runners. Blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic) is lower for sprinters and higher in Long distance runners. So it is understood that the resting pulse rate and pulse pressure is better in Long distance runners than sprinters and blood pressure (Systolic) and blood pressure (Diastolic) is better in sprinters than Long distance runners.

It is clear from the table value that resting pulse rate, blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic) has been significant difference between Sprinters and Long distance runners. Pulse pressure has been found insignificant difference between Sprinters and Long distance runners, since the computed value of t for all the dimensions were greater than the tabulated $t_{0.05 (19)} = 2.02$ except pulse pressure ($t = 0.75$). Thus it may be concluded that the all the circulatory indices except pulse pressure among Sprinters and Long distance runners sportsmen found to be statistically significant.

Figure 1 Indicate the Mean values (\pm SD), standard error of the mean and test statistic t of pulse rate, blood

pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic) and pulse pressure of Sprinters and Long distance runners ($N = 20$).

Fig. 1: Circulatory Indices of Sprinters and Long Distance Runners

DISCUSSION

The calculation of circulatory indices has shown that there was a significant difference on resting pulse rate, blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic) between Sprinters and Long distance runners. Pulse pressure has been found insignificant difference between Sprinters and Long distance runners, since the computed value of t for all the indices were greater than the tabulated $t_{0.05 (19)} = 2.02$ except pulse pressure ($t = 0.75$). Thus it may be concluded that all the circulatory indices except pulse pressure among Sprinters and Long distance runners found to be statistically significant.

As per the finding Long distance runners were better than Sprinters on resting pulse rate, blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic), the finding of this study is supported by the finding of Oring and Jamison.

The finding of Moutis are in disagreement with the Finding of this investigation that of having insignificant difference on pulse pressure. These reasons could be attributed to not getting significant differences on the indices as mentioned above.

Table 1: The Significant of Mean Difference, Standard Error of the Mean and Test Statistic t of on Circulatory Indices of Sprinters and Long Distance Runners

Group Variable	Mean		SD		SEM	T-value	P-value
	Sprinters	Long Runners	Sprinters	Long Runners	Sprinters		
Resting Pulse Rate(RPR)	62.7	58	4.46	6.40	1.32	3.18*	0.05
Blood Pressure (Systolic)	105.1	108.7	6.45	5.68	1.85	3.45*	0.02
Blood Pressure (Diastolic)	74	74.15	7.23	7.42	1.79	2.72*	0.008
Pulse Pressure (PP)	45.2	44.95	7.22	6.18	1.49	0.75	0.40

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CONCLUSION

In the light of conclusion drawn and within the limitations of the study, it can be revealed that our bodily system have been gifted by nature to accommodate themselves and change the functions accordingly within the physiological limits. This has been responded by cardio-vascular system by increasing the pulse pressure which increases the amount of blood flow through lungs. Minutes to compensate the deficient oxygenation of blood.

No significant changes were found in pulse pressure of the Sprinters and Long distance runners. Hence, it can be concluded that the physical activity may help the athletes by involving the adaptation power of their cardio-vascular.

After giving a deep view of all the tables, it can be observed that there is not much of difference in the blood pressure for Sprinters, which indicates that due to the physical activity. The individuals maintain certain physical values to the optimum level.

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